

Corpus-Based Analysis of Demonyms in Slovene Twitter

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Abstract

This paper reports on a corpus-based analysis of demonym mentions in the corpus of Slovene tweets. First, we analyze the frequency of demonym mentions for the inhabitants of the European and G8 countries. Then, we focus on the representation of demonyms for residents of Slovenia's neighboring countries: Austria, Italy, Hungary and Croatia. The main topic of the tweets mentioning Croatians, Austrians and Italians is sport, whereas Hungarians occur most often in relation to the Eurovision. Some economic and political issues are also represented, such as the selling of Slovene companies to foreign firms, the refugee crisis and the arbitration procedure between Slovenia and Croatia. A collocation analysis revealed a highly stereotypical treatment of the neighboring nations and hostility of some Slovene Twitter users to inhabitants of Slovenia's neighboring countries.

Keywords: demonyms, nationalities, Twitter, discourse analysis, Slovene

1. Introduction

A corpus of user-generated content, especially of tweets, offers an insight into people's beliefs, opinions and attitudes, including attitudes towards residents of other countries. This paper presents an analysis of demonyms (i.e. nouns, used to denote inhabitants of a particular city, country etc.) for the nations which are members of the European Union and of non-European G8 nations that are mentioned in the corpus of Slovene tweets Janes Tweet v4.0 in order to analyze how often Slovene Twitter users talk about other nationalities and in which contexts. Next, a detailed analysis of the representation of the neighboring nationalities was performed in order to establish the general attitude of Slovene Twitter users towards their neighbors.

2. Related Work

Phrases that appear together multiple times provide cultural information and analyzing them can "provide empirical evidence of how the culture is expressed in lexical patterns" (Stubbs, 1996: 169). It is therefore not surprising that many corpus-based discourse analyses have been conducted to observe how people present other nations in written text.

For instance, Bang (2008) examined the representation of foreign countries in the corpus of US news reports. The premodifiers of the keywords 'country', 'countries', 'nation' and 'nations' were analyzed, and collocates indicating verbal and mental actions of Arab and European leaders were examined. Furthermore, the lexical collocates of 'said' and the grammatical collocates of keywords 'China', 'North Korea', 'South Korea' and 'Japan' were analyzed. The study revealed that the representation of foreign counties in US news reports is characterized by stereotyping and asymmetry (ibid.).

Similarly, Tarasheva (2009) used critical discourse analysis to study the representation of Bulgaria in a corpus of articles, published on the BBC website.

Articles about Bulgaria were compared to the ones about Belgium, Portugal, Finland and Denmark in a comparable corpora. The research examined the topics of the articles, most frequent keywords and collocations. The results showed that events from Bulgaria are presented differently than those from the other examined countries: articles about crime appear much more often and the most frequent keywords indicate that Bulgarians are mainly portrayed as crime victims. Tarasheva (2009) concludes that "negative coverage for Bulgaria is deliberately sought and achieved".

Our study differs from other corpus-based work mentioned above in that it does not examine texts ordered, authored and edited by professionals but rather unsolicited user-generated content posted by the general public.

In contrast to the abundance of corpus-based studies of representations of countries, representations of inhabitants have not yet received much attention. However, the complex topic regarding the Slovenes' attitudes towards their neighbors has been the subject of many academic works. Throughout history, Slovenes lived in multicultural countries – until the early 20th century in the Austro-Hungarian Empire and then in Yugoslavia until the 1990s (Zupančič & Arbeiter, 2016). Furthermore, during the world wars, they were occupied by Italians, Austrians and Hungarians. Hence, Slovenes began to perceive themselves as inferior to their neighbors. Moreover, they perceived them as their enemies and felt threatened by them (Romih, 2013). Thus, Slovenes have become introverted and developed negative attitudes towards their neighbors in order to feel superior to them as well as to strengthen their nationalistic feelings (Šabec, 2007; Zupančič & Arbeiter, 2016). The growth of negative attitudes has also been influenced by the media in former Yugoslavia which tended to portray other nations as crude and violent (Zupančič & Arbeiter, 2016). Today, Slovenes still distrust their neighbors, especially Croatians, who are perceived to be the least trustworthy peoples from former

Yugoslavia, according to surveys in 2009 and 2010 (Salihović, 2012).

3. The Janes v4.0 Tweet Corpus

The Janes v4.0 Tweet corpus is a subcorpus of Slovene user-generated corpus Janes (Fišer et al., 2016), which contains tweets, written by Slovene Twitter users in the period June 2013–July 2016. The corpus contains 107 million tokens and has been richly linguistically annotated (rediacritization, word-form normalization, part-of-speech tagging and lemmatization) and enriched with metadata, obtained directly from the Twitter API (author, title, time of post, number of retweets and favorites), but also through specialized processes, e.g. sentiment (“neutral”, “positive” or “negative”), the gender of the author, the type of the user (“private” for individuals or “corporate” for companies, news agencies etc.) and the linguistic and technical level of (non)standardness of the text.

4. Demonyms in the Slovene Twittosphere

4.1 Subcorpus

The study was performed in the Sketch Engine concordancer. For the purposes of our study, we constructed a subcorpus of tweets, written by individuals (annotated as “private”) in the Slovene language. The subcorpus contains 77,250,014 tokens.

Since we were interested in opinions of the general public, we only examined private users’ tweets in order to exclude tweets from companies or news outlets that often have a persuasive function, trying to influence the readers’ opinion or attract customers.

4.2 Methodology

In the first part of the study, we examined the frequency of demonym mentions for inhabitants of all European

nations that were part of European Union in April, 2017 (including Great Britain) and of non-European members of the G8 (Canada, Japan, Russia and the USA). Due to length restrictions of this paper, only official demonyms as they occur in the Slovene orthography manual *Slovenski pravopis* (Toporišič et al., 2014) were analyzed. We examined the occurrence of both masculine and feminine form of demonyms.

4.3 Results

As can be seen from Figure 1, Slovene Twitter users most frequently mention their southern neighbors, Croatians, much more often than inhabitants of other neighboring countries. After Croatians, Slovene tweets most frequently feature residents from the most influential nations of the world—Germany, Russia and the United States of America—which is not surprising as the actions of these countries have a profound influence on the rest of the world. Interestingly, Greeks also occur frequently: regarding a random sample of tweets, we could presume that Slovene Twitter users mostly mention Greeks in connection with the economic crisis in Greece and when commenting their decisions regarding the European Union, as they have an important impact on the economic and political situation in the whole European Union. The least frequent demonyms represent residents of smaller European nations, such as Luxembourg, Cyprus, Malta etc.

Feminine forms of all nationality names are rather rare, which is not surprising as in Slovene the masculine form of the demonym is used as the generic noun that includes both men and women. The only feminine form that stands out is the form for ‘Slovene woman’ *Slovenka*. It must also be taken into account that when users generalize actions of members of their own nation, they likely substitute ‘Slovenes’ by ‘us’. That could be the reason why the frequency of the demonym ‘Slovenes’ (*Slovensci*) is lower than frequency of ‘Croatians’, ‘Germans’ etc.

Figure 1: Frequency of Selected Demonyms in Slovene Twitter Corpus

5. Representations of the Neighboring Nations

5.1 Methodology

In the second part of the study, the representations of demonyms for Slovenia's neighboring nations were compared. The keywords *Avstrijec*, *Avstrijka* (masculine and feminine form for 'Austrian'), *Italijan*, *Italijanka* (masculine and feminine form for 'Italian'), *Madžar*, *Madžarka* (masculine and feminine form for 'Hungarian') and *Hrvat*, *Hrvatica* (masculine and feminine form for 'Croatian') were examined in terms of the users that mentioned them (frequency of different users, their gender), the annotated sentiment of the tweets, the number of retweets and favorites and the topics of the tweets. Furthermore, the collocations of these keywords with nouns, adjectives and verbs were analyzed. The aim of this part of the study was to analyze how often Slovenes mention their neighbors and in connection with which topic, whether these tweets receive a lot of attention and what the general attitude of Slovenes towards their neighbors is.

The same subcorpus and concordancer were used as in Section 4. The analysis was conducted using the metadata in the corpus. Collocation analysis was performed with the Word Sketch feature in the Sketch Engine. However, it was limited to masculine forms of the nationality names as the frequency of the feminine forms was too low. All collocations that appeared five times or more were examined. Topics of the tweets in which the relevant nationalities were mentioned were deducted from the accompanying hashtags. Tweets without hashtags were not considered in this final step.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Metadata

As was already shown in Section 4, Slovene Twitter users most often talk about Croatians: 6,285 tweets were found that contain either masculine or feminine form of this demonym. The second most mentioned neighbors of Slovenes are Italians with 2,231 hits, closely followed by Austrians with 2,068 hits, while Hungarians are mentioned in only 952 tweets. Tweets mentioning Hungarians had the highest frequency of different users, which means that a user rarely wrote about Hungarians more than once; whereas there is the largest number of users who recurrently wrote about Croatians.

A very small amount of all tweets containing demonyms was retweeted (7) or favorited (20) more than 20 times. Tweets mentioning Croatians were retweeted or favorited the most, which is not unusual, given that 'Croatian' is the most frequent demonym mentioned by Slovene Twitter users. Interestingly, the most retweeted (47 times) and favorited (119 times) tweet does not refer to Croatians, but to Austrians. As feminine forms of demonyms rarely appear, it is not surprising that the most

retweeted post, containing feminine form of a demonym, was retweeted only 17 times, mentioning Italian women. Approximately three quarters of tweets, featuring masculine forms, were written by men. Surprisingly, feminine forms are much more frequently used by feminine users (*Hrvatica* 'Croatian woman'—39% of authors of tweets were females, *Italijanka* 'Italian woman'—52%, *Avstrijka* 'Austrian woman'—45% and *Madžarka* 'Hungarian woman'—24%).

While the sentiment of tweets containing the masculine form of demonyms are mostly negative, tweets with the feminine form are mostly neutral, except tweets containing *Avstrijka* 'Austrian woman', which are mostly negative. However, in comparison with others, the demonym for Austrian women also has the largest percentage of positive tweets (25%). Positive tweets, which represent 17%–25% of all hits, are the least frequent for all examined nationality names. Interestingly, more than half of the tweets about Hungarians are negative, which makes this nationality the most negatively presented, according to the sentiment annotation.

5.2.2 Collocations

The analysis of demonym + noun collocations revealed not only that analyzed demonyms almost exclusively appear in coordination with other demonyms, mostly with demonyms for residents of Slovenia's neighboring countries. Interestingly, Croatians co-occur with Slovenes much more often than the other three demonyms. Croatians also frequently occurs in coordination with demonyms for inhabitants from the Balkans (Serbians and Bosnians). Italians and Austrians frequently co-occur with Germans. Hungarians appear more often in connection with Italians, Croatians, Austrians, Czechs and Slovaks than with Slovenes.

Due to a low frequency count, no adjective + demonym collocations that pass the frequency threshold (5) were found for *Madžar* 'Hungarian'. On the other hand, *Hrvat* 'Croatian', *Avstrijec* 'Austrian' and *Italijan* 'Italian' collocate with various different adjectives, which indicate how differently they are represented in Slovene Twitter.

'Croatian' collocates with adjectives that are otherwise associated with Slovenes: *podalpski* 'sub-alpine', *alpski* 'alpine' and *brdski* 'from the hills'. These adjectives are used in order to shock readers and to declare that Slovenes are becoming Croatians, or acting as them, as in the tweet "Unfortunately, too many Slovenes are actually Alpine Croatians." (*Žal je preveč Slovencev v resnici Alpskih Hrvatov.*). Furthermore, most adjectives that collocate with 'Croatian' are used ironically. Such adjective is 'poor' (*ubog*) as in "Poor Croatians are left with only 1,000 km of coast..." (*Ubogim Hrvatom ostane samo še 1000 km obale ...*) Positive adjectives 'grand' (*veliki*) and 'dear' (*dragi*) are also used ironically. Another adjective that also occurs frequently with this keyword is 'guilty' (*kriv*). It mostly appears in ironic

tweets in which users mock Slovene tendency to blame Croats for everything, for example “Listening to the news reports, one would say that Croats are guilty for the unpreparedness of our government.” (*Po poročanju medijev bi človek rekel, da so za nepripravljenost naše vlade krivi Hrvati.*) Furthermore, ‘Croatian’ also collocates with ‘true’ (*pravi*) in tweets from which stereotypes about Croats can be easily presumed. Such example is “Refugees are not true Croats. True Croats never flee” (*Begunci niso pravi Hrvati. Pravi Hrvat nikoli ne beži.*)

In contrast, ‘Italian’ and ‘Austrian’ do not appear in collocations with adjectives that are used ironically. ‘Italian’ mostly collocates with ‘loud’ (*glasen*), which is generally perceived as a negative trait. That can be seen from the following example: “So a coffee in peace changed into ‘a coffee in a coffee shop, filled with loud Italians.’ Yay” (*In kava v miru se je spremenila v ‘kava v kafiču polnem glasnih italijanov’. Yay.*) Interestingly, a collocation ‘old Italian’ (*star Italijan*) also occurs quite often, mostly with a negative connotation, as in “What, can these old Italians smell in which sauna is a woman. Suddenly, a whole bunch of them is next to her” (*Kva ti stari italijani zavohajo v keru savni je ženska. Naenkrat jih je cel kombi ob njej.*)

The keyword ‘Austrian’ frequently collocates only with one adjective, which is ‘rich’ (*bogat*). It appears mostly in its superlative form, for instance as in “This year, the richest Austrian is 80 times richer than the richest Slovene” (*Najbogatejši Avstrijec je letos 80-krat bogatejši od najbogatejšega Slovenca.*)

As the direct object, the nouns ‘Croatian’ and ‘Italian’ frequently appear with the verb ‘to defeat’ (*premagati*). This collocation appears in connection with sport and Slovene Twitter users mostly hope that their team or foreign teams would beat Croats or Italians and tweet about it with excitement when it happens. A collocation ‘to have a Croatian for neighbor’ (*imeti Hrvata za soseda*) also occurs quite often. Generally, there is not enough context to determine whether this is meant in a positive or negative way. However, there are some very telling examples which are clearly negative, such as “Who needs an enemy when you have a Croatian for a neighbor!” (*Kdo rabi sovražnika če imaš Hrvata za soseda!*). Furthermore, the verb ‘to hate’ also co-occurs relatively frequently with Croats, but it was discovered that it actually occurs in only one sentence that had been then retweeted by different users: “Who doesn’t hate Croats, ain’t Slovene” (*Kdor ne sovraži Hrvatov, ni Slovenec*—an allusion to a Slovene popular soccer fan slogan “Who doesn’t jump, ain’t Slovene”).

The keywords ‘Croatian’ and ‘Austrian’ often collocate with the verb ‘to sell’ (*prodati*), as Slovene Twitter users mention or disapprove the fact that many Slovene firms have been sold to Croatian and Austrian companies.

The keyword ‘Italian’ frequently collocates with the verb ‘support’ (*navijati*), connected with sport. In most analyzed tweets, Twitter users declare (sometimes surprised) that they support the Italian team. Such

example is “I see that you support the Italian football team. And I support the Croats. Who would thought so?!” (*navijaš za italijane u fuzbalu, vidim. Jst za hrvate. Kdu bi si mislil..?!*) In contrast to that, ‘Italian’ also quite often appears with *ne marati*, meaning ‘dislike’. However, these tweets seem much less negative than tweets about Croats and some have a positive turn, as in “I don’t like Italians, but today I supported them” (*ne maram italijanov ampak danes sem za njih navijal.*)

5.2.3 Topics

As can be already presumed from the collocations of the keywords with verbs, frequency analysis of hashtags shows that the topic of a majority of the tweets mentioning ‘Croats’, ‘Austrians’ and ‘Italians’ is sport (e.g. #eurobasket, #sochi...). The only exception are Hungarians, for which the most frequent topic is Eurovision, also a popular topic in tweets with the other three demonyms. In terms of politics, a number of hashtags relate to the arbitration procedure to define border between Slovenia and Croatia, as well as to refugees.

6. Conclusion

In this paper we examined demonym mentions in the corpus of Slovene tweets. The results showed that Slovene Twitter users mostly talk about their southern neighbors, Croats. According to sentiment annotation, tweets comprising masculine forms of demonyms for Slovenia’s neighboring countries are mostly negative, while feminine forms mostly occur in neutral tweets. The collocation analysis revealed that Croats are generally disliked by the Slovene Twitter users, occurring in ironic or negative context that presents them as unwanted neighbors and reveals deeply rooted stereotypes. Italians are presented as being sometimes unpleasant, but still more likeable than Croats. When referring to Austrians, Slovene Twitter users mostly connect them with being rich (or richer than Slovenes). Hashtag analysis revealed that Slovenes predominantly mention these nationalities in connection with sport. Some events and political issues are also represented, such as the selling of Slovene companies to Croatian and Austrian firms, the refugee crisis and the arbitration procedure between Slovenia and Croatia.

The analysis was sometimes difficult as some errors in annotation occurred due to polysemy and multilinguality issues (e.g. *Danka* ‘Danish woman’ or *danka* ‘rectum’, *Japonka* ‘Japanese woman’ or *japonka* ‘slipper’, *Maltežan* ‘Maltese man’ or *maltežan* ‘Maltese dog’). The results are also limited because there were included only official demonyms.

The corpus offers numerous opportunities for extending the research, e.g. the usage of derogatory or discriminatory terms for nationalities, representation of the peoples from the Balkans, as well as comparison between the representation of various nationalities by private and corporate Twitter accounts.

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